

SYNTHESIS OF CIS-2-UNSATURATED FATTY ACIDS FOR BIOCHEMICAL CONTROL OF BIOFILM PRODUCTION IN XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA

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Different chemical species are utilized from bacteria as signals for cell-to-cell communication during Quorum Sensing. A widely investigated family of chemical signals from plant pathogenic bacteria are the diffusible signal factors (DSFs). In *Xylella fastidiosa* and related *Xanthomonas* species, these DSFs are produced by a synthase (RpfF) and interact with a cognate sensor (RpfC), resulting in the activation of a response regulator (RpfG) able of coordinating genes involved in the expression of virulence, spreading and biofilm formation. By recent investigations, *X. fastidiosa* exploits cis-2-unsaturated fatty acids as its own DSFs, and an imbalance in their concentration in bacterial cells seem to provoke blockage of xylem infection, by altering biofilm formation and architecture in a strategy called "pathogen confusion". Here we report the synthesis of cis-2-unsaturated fatty acids with a chemical structure related to DSFs family, in order to test the *in vitro* alteration of biofilm production in *X. fastidiosa* 'De Donno' strain, the etiological agent of Olive Quick Decline Syndrome in Apulia region.

A modified olefination stereoselective reaction of Horner-Emmons, called Still-Gennari, allowed for the synthesis of α - β unsaturated fatty acids in cis (Z) conformation starting from commercial aldehydes. A preliminary investigation is carried out testing different commercial cis-2-unsaturated fatty acids (cis-2-decenoic acid, cis-2-dodecenoic acid, cis-2-(11)-methyl-dodecenoic acid) known as DSFs in *Xanthomonas*, *Burkholderia* and *Pseudomonas* genera, for their effect on *X. fastidiosa* ability to form a biofilm ring adhering to the surface of glass tubes or microtiter plates. These *in vitro* assays will be used to test the synthesized α - β unsaturated fatty acids.